

1 **Kinase targeting in basal-like breast cancer: VRK1.**

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5 Breast cancer can be distinguished into two broad groups, luminal and basal, based on cytologic,
6 morphologic, cytoskeletal and differentiation-based features. While luminal breast cancers can be positive
7 accordingly clinically, basal-like breast cancers cannot. Inadequate long-term control of disease (e.g.,
8 partial response [PR] or recurrence/relapse) reflects limited effectiveness of existing drugs that treat basal
9 subtype disease. Here we utilized whole transcriptome technologies (5, 6) to define the basal-like breast
10 cancer kinome and phosphatome by measuring total transcription in the primary tumors of humans with
11 basal-like as compared to luminal A and luminal B breast cancer to identify basal-like signaling features.
12 We describe one member of a group of kinases up-regulated and differentially expressed in human
13 basal-like breast cancer, VRK1, as a catalytically available enzyme and candidate therapeutic target for
14 the adjunctive medical treatment of basal subtype breast cancer.
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CRISPR-based reverse genetic screening of human basal subtype and triple negative organoids or primary tumor cells freshly isolated from patients with basal subtype breast cancers or TNBC with limited exposure to artificial culture conditions have not yet been described (7, 8). These genetic technologies, though not yet implemented, when done so will likely facilitate discovery of therapeutic vulnerabilities in basal subtype disease with rapidity and ease.

We utilize genomic and transcriptomic technologies to study the genomic sequences (DNA), the transcriptome (RNA), and epigenetic modification (eg., CpG-DNA) of humans with breast cancer. This includes the primary tumor, the source of the transformation - like mutant variants of p53 - subtypes of the primary tumor, including luminal, basal and HER2+ forms, "regional" metastasis to the lymph nodes, metastasis to distant sites, including the lungs, the liver and the brain, and the circulating tumor stem cell. Our hypothesis and working strategy dictates that in the short-run, disease complications and therapeutic limitations are best managed using identification of therapeutic targets by whole transcriptome differential expression analyses (subtraction analysis), and in the long-run, will be enhanced and fully complemented by reverse genetic screening strategies to blindly identify subtype-specific and metastasis-specific therapeutic vulnerabilities augmented by novel immunotherapy approaches. Here we describe one such target identified through study of the basal-like tumor transcriptome: a kinase target that is up-regulated, catalytically available and subtype-specific: VRK1.

Results

Figure 1: VRK1 is differentially expressed in basal subtype breast cancer.

I. Primary tumors of the breast from humans with breast cancer: basal subtype

n=59 luminal A and luminal B breast cancer
n=43 basal subtype breast cancer

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
203856_at	4.60E-13	-8.3131538	19.17216	-1.09614999	VRK1	1810/29873	93.9

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the tumors of humans with luminal A breast cancer or luminal B breast cancer as compared to that of basal subtype breast cancer (5), we discovered differential expression of vaccinia related kinase 1, encoded by *VRK1* in basal subtype breast cancer in humans (**Chart 1**). The expression of *VRK1* changed more than nearly 95% of the human breast tumor transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 29,873 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of *VRK1* messenger RNA in basal subtype tumors, suggesting up-regulation of *VRK1* during transformation and lineage specification of the breast to the basal breast cancer subtype.

II. Primary tumors of the breast from humans with breast cancer: basal subtype

n=77 luminal A and luminal B breast cancer
n=14 basal-like breast cancer

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
7976621	2.95e-05	-4.3951058	1.96322	-0.71496148	VRK1	2351/33297	92.9

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the primary tumors of humans with luminal A and luminal B breast cancers relative to basal subtype breast cancers in a second microarray dataset (6)

1 from independent investigators and a separate patient cohort, we validated differential expression of VRK1
2 in basal subtype breast cancer in humans (**Chart 2**). The expression of VRK1 here changed more than
3 90% of the human breast tumor transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was
4 measured - in this case, 33,297 transcripts (“Rank”). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased
5 quantity of VRK1 messenger RNA in basal subtype tumors, suggesting up-regulation of VRK1 during
6 transformation and lineage specification of the breast to the basal breast cancer subtype.

7 Thus, differential and increased expression of VRK1 defines the transcriptional landscape of the
8 basal or basal-like breast cancer subtype in humans.

9 **Discussion**

10 Adjunctive treatments in medical oncology limit the emergence of resistant tumor clones during
11 treatment with a second treatment (whether neoadjuvant chemotherapy or a targeted therapy like
12 tamoxifen and letrozole). We recently used primary tumor transcriptome data to identify multiple
13 phosphatases that we deemed candidate therapeutic targets in management of breast cancer, and
14 fortuitously found their decreased expression was specifically linked to superior overall survival in patients
15 with another subtype of breast cancer, HER2+ breast cancer (14, 15). A multi-kinase approach delivered
16 in conjunction with chemotherapies that target dNTP synthesis, replication of the daughter strand and
17 activity at the spindle at anaphase is most likely to be most effective in limiting tumor clone resistance (16).
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Methods

We utilized GSE45827 for this tumor transcriptome study, measuring whole transcription in basal subtype primary tumors from humans with breast cancer, as compared to luminal A or luminal B breast cancers (along with GSE87049 for target validation) using microarray data (published) and R-based computational methods (GEO2R).